

Digital Transformation and Good Governance

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Abstract

Digital transformation significantly impacts good governance by enhancing transparency, accountability, citizen engagement and efficiency in government operations through features like online services delivery, data driven decision making and accessible information, ultimately leading to more responsive and inclusive governing system. This paper will focus on evolution process of digital transformation which enhances the effectiveness of good governance. Additionally, the objective of this paper is to make people aware about digital tools with the aim in the mind of making citizen centric system. Moreover, paper discusses impact of digital tools in different sectors such as education, health and judiciary. Consequently, will discuss its challenges of digital transformation, how excessive dependability and reliability hinder the human capacity and manpower and what the government initiatives that enhance the capacity.

Key words: Digital transformation, digital divide, Good Governance, transparency and accountability

Introduction

Digital transformation presents a significant opportunity to enhance good governance by enabling greater transparency; citizen engagement and efficient service delivery, at the same time require a fully fledged to address potential challenges and ensure inclusive access to technology. Digital transformation has an impact on all aspects of life, from the economy to government from geopolitics to the way in which ordinary people interact. In the last twenty years, the Council of Europe has worked on issues such as e – democracy, e – governance, internet governance, the use of artificial intelligence in different sectors preventing discrimination due to biased algorithms, and the manipulation use of social media in election campaigns.

Digital transformation refers to the use of digital technologies, tools and applications of any kind from digitization of processes to blockchain and artificial intelligence. Applied to government and public administration, digital transformation enables new ways of functioning, engaging with citizens and civil society at large and providing services to the public. Good Governance endorse responsiveness, rule of law, participation, Representation, fair conduct of elections, openness and transparency, Ethical conduct, Competence and Capacity, all these facets helpful to increase the capacity of digital

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governance.² Increased transparency of online platforms allow citizens to access government, documents and decision making processes reality, promoting greater scrutiny and accountability.

Improved service delivery of digital services like online applications and portals streamlines citizen interactions with government agencies, making services accessible to all citizens faster and convenient. Utilizing large database collected through digital interactions enables government to make informed policy decisions based on real time insights and citizen needs. Digital platforms facilitate citizen participation in policy discussions, feedback mechanisms and public consultations, promoting a more inclusive governance approach. Streamlining administrations tasks through digitalization can lead to operational affiance and reduced administrative costs. Digital transformation in government involves the utilization of innovative technologies in order to deliver more transparent, cost effective and customer oriented services to citizens at both national & local level.

Evolution of digital transformation

Digital transformation started evolving around 20th century, In 1980, 1990 different organisations & agencies started to leverage technology primarily for operational efficiency and automation tasks, Usage of electronic data interchange started from 1970s & 1980s this strategy is quite useful for businesses to exchange documents electronically, reducing reliability on paper and speed up the transaction, 1990s was the time which significant milestone with proliferation of the World Wide Web and dot com boom. The introduction of web browsers in the early 1990s such as Mosaic and Netscape navigator make internet more accessible and user friendly leading to an explosion of web activity. Amazon came in 1994 and e – bay launched in 1995, significant in harnessing the emerging digital landscape, it was the liberation period when introduce e – commerce and online business emerged as revolution.

Dot Com facility started in 2000s which support sustainable digital business models. During this period, past crash surviving businesses focused on creating value through technology, leading to the rise of software as a service (SaaS) models and broader adoption of enterprise resources planning (ERP) to integrate and automate business processes. The transformational phase of 2010s depict majority of strategic integration of

² Millard, Jeremy. (2023). *Impact of Digital transformation on public governance. Joint Research Centre (Seville Site), 2023*

digital technologies into all businesses. It was the time of cloud computing platforms like Amazon, Web series (AWS), Microsoft Azure and Google cloud.

Challenges of Digital transformation

Old System: These old system are not compatible with modern strategies. In fact, these outdated systems hinder the integration of new digital solution which make difficult for government to keep pace with technological advancements.

Prevalence of soiled data and system: It impedes information sharing across different government department and agencies.

Resistance to change: It is another obstacle to successful digital transformation. Some people community reluctant to change and embrace new technologies fearing of losing job is another reason to feel overwhelmed by the need to learn new skills.

Limited resources and funding: Government may face budgetary constraints that restrict their ability to invest in the necessary infrastructure software.³

Digital transformation that solve redressal issues

Centralised Public Grievance redress and monitoring system (CPGRAMS) is a platform available online all day to lodge their grievances to the public authorities on any matter related to service delivery. It is a single portal connected to all the Ministries/Departments of Government of India and states. Every ministry and states have role based accessibility to the system. CPGRAMS is also accessible to the citizens through standalone mobile application downloadable through Google play store and mobile application integrated with UMANG. CPGRAMS also provides appeal facility to the citizens if they are not satisfied with the resolution by grievance officer.

- 1) CPGRAMS is a universalization routing of grievances to the last mile.
- 2) Technological enhancements automation in 22 Scheduled languages along with English.
- 3) Grievance Redressal Index ranking of ministries/departments on their performance.
- 4) Feedback call centre – 50 Seater call centre to collect feedback directly from every citizen whose grievance is redressed.

³ Zysman J, Feldman Stuart, Murray Jonathan, Nielsen Christian Niels & Kushida E Kenji. (2011). *the new challenge to economic governance: The digital transformation of Services*

- 5) One Nation One Portal – Integration of state portal and other portals with CPGRAMS.
- 6) Training and Capacity building conducting by ISTM and State AITs under SEVOTTAM Scheme for enabling effective grievance resolution.⁴
- 7) CPGRAM also available in different languages such as English, Assamese, Bengali, Gujarati, Hindi, Kannada, Kashmiri, Konkani, Malayalam, Manipuri, Marathi, Nepali, Oriya, Punjabi, Sanskrit, Sindhi, Tamil. Telugu, Urdu, Bado, Santhali, Maithili and Dogri.

Digital Platform for effective grievance redressal in states

State Governments have evolved advanced mechanisms for redressal of public grievances cells which receive complaints from citizens and forward those to the concerned departments and follow them up. In several states, senior officers visited districts and villages as part of Good Governance week celebrations in 2021 & 2022 when nationwide campaigns for effective redressal of public grievance were conducted.⁵

State	Scheme
Gujarat	SWAGAT
Jammu & Kashmir	JKIGRAMS
Andhra Pradesh	SPANDANA
Uttarakhand	CM helpline
Telangana	Prajavaani
Uttar Pradesh	JANSUNWAI Portal
Kerala	CM's PG Redressal Cell
Rajasthan	Rajasthan Sampark
Maharashtra	Aaple Sarkar
Madhya Pradesh	CM Helpline
Odisha	E – Abhijoga
Bihar	Bihar Jan Shikayat Nivaran

Government Initiatives to improve Digital Transformation

1) MyGov

⁴ <https://services.india.gov.in/service/detail/centralised-public-grievance-redress-and-monitoring-system-cpgrams>

⁵ *Empowering Consumers The Evolution and Challenges of Grievance Redressal in Digital Age . (2024). Cuts international, Jaipur, India*

- 2) Digital India
- 3) CoWIN
- 4) DigiLocker
- 5) Cloud Computing adoption
- 6) Digital Skill Gap

Impact of Digital transformation on different sector

Health

Digital transformation across different sectors involves utilizing digital technologies like cloud computing, AI, IoT and data Analytics to significantly change how businesses operate within their respective industries, impacting everything from customer interactions to internal processes. In financial sector, implementation of mobile banking, AI powered fraud detection, personalized wealth management and started using blockchain technique for transactions. In health sector, Telemedicine, electronic health records (EHR) are useful to analytically design the management system, use AI in health sector becoming new treatment technique. Using data to identify high risk patients and proactively manage their health.

Digital transformation in healthcare is the use of digital technologies to improve the condition of health sector and also helpful to improve delivery process of healthcare services. Healthcare sector involves data analytics, innovative processes to enhance healthcare services. Health system considers digital capabilities a path to fundamentally transform their relationship with consumers. To meet consumers needs healthcare sector must consider accelerating their digital transformation efforts by establishing a governance model, creating a digital culture, recruiting and retaining the right talent.

Many hospitals and health system adopt digital technologies as numerous initiatives from installing electronic health record (EHR) systems to building apps to trying disruptive or innovative technique such as artificial Intelligence (AI). Digital tools give healthcare providers an extensive view of patient health by significantly increasing the accessibility to health. They use such information to prevent disease, lower healthcare costs and design interventions tailored for the needs of individual patients. Digital health applications can also augment human decision making by automating and accelerating labour intensive tasks. Few hospitals use digital monitoring tools to track patient safety

metrics like hospital acquired infections or hand hygiene compliance in real as well as other systems to streamline workspace.⁶

Education

Digital transformation in education sector support the process of fundamental changes of how educational institutions operate by leveraging digital technologies, including online platforms, interactive tools, data analytics to enhance student learning experiences, improve communication between teachers, students and parents and streamline administrative tasks often leading to more personalized and flexible learning environments. Online learning platforms for delivery online course materials, virtual classrooms and remote learning options are unable to access education beyond traditional classroom limitations. Incorporation of game mechanics into learning activities to increase engagement and motivation, making learning fun activity and increase social engagement among students.

Using data to track student progress identify areas of improvement and inform instructional decisions leading to more targeted teaching strategies. Utilizing immersive technologies to create simulated environments for hands – on – learning experience and create cultural activities. Utilizing online platform for real time collaboration between students, teachers and peers promoting teamwork and communication. Through education, it increased accessibility & provides education to students in remote locations or with disabilities may face barriers to traditional learning. Interactive learning experience has a capacity to boost student interest and participation. Personalized learning and targeted interventions can lead to better academic performance.⁷

Judiciary

Digital tools are capable to improve justice sector efficiency, transparency and accessibility to justice. Establishment of e – justice can advance the rule of law and protect human rights, whereas also improve the effectiveness of justice system. But technology can also be used in many ways that exacerbate injustice, negatively impact rights and freedoms. Identifying and understanding both the opportunities and the risks of technology is critical for fully releasing its role in advancing justice, human rights and rule of law.

⁶ Kraus, Sascha, Schiavone, Pluzhnikova Anna, Invernizzi, Anna Chaira. (2021). *Digital Transformation in healthcare: Analyzing the current state of research. Journal of Business Research*

⁷ k. katyeudo, de S. Oliveira, AC Ricard & Souza De. (2021). *Digital Transformation towards Education 4.0. Infomatics in Education*

Digital transformation in the justice sector accelerated as governments embraced updated platforms for online filing, digital processes and virtual courts, new momentum was given to longstanding calls for the modernisation and digitalisation of justice service the world.⁸ Covid 19 restriction provided a major breakthrough to digitalisation of Indian courts. It is witness that judiciary system led by system court and high courts, adopted e-filing urgent matters and conducted frequent hearing over video conferencing. Digitalization of Indian Judiciary presents a golden opportunity to reduce the pendency of a plethora of cases and preserve the decade old documents. In 2006, e – courses were launched as part of the National e – Governace (NeGP). The vision document for phase III of the e – courts project was introduced during the Covid 19 pandemic to address the judiciary’s digital deprivation⁹.

Law Minister has said that fo implementing phase of the e – courts project, there is need to adopt new cutting edge technologies of Machine learning (ML) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) to increase the efficiency the efficiency of the justice delivery system, because of excess amount of physical records demand severe need for digitalisation, time courts to the appellate courts is as of the major factors that cause delays in cases. Role of judges and lawyers political will and the support of judge and lawyers are necessary for digitalisation process to succeed. Need of the hour is for them to be made aware of the associated technologies and receive adequate training conduct training sessions framework and procedure can give a huge impetus to the successful running of e – courts.

Virtue hearing should be mandatory as some cases identified by the court administration. Digitalisation of court administration digitalisation of court through electronic court case management information System (ECCMIS) enhance record keeping and reduce delays and case back logs by automating and standardizing manual procedures, reduce human to human interaction thereby making it technologically and practically different to engage in corrupt tendencies. The use of digital application systems can also be an effective way to prevent potential court practices and maladministration in the courts and it allows the public to monitor the activities of the courts a closely.

⁸ *Djamaludin, Aziz Muhammad Fahrudin, Rasyid, Yanuriansyah Ar & Sayyis Iskandar Ali. (2023). Assessing the Impact of Electronic Court systems on the efficiency of judicial Processes in the Era of Digital Transformation. Volksgeist*

⁹ *Batool S, Gill Ali Shahzad, Javaid Saba, Ali Junaid Khan. (2021). Good Governance via E – Governance: moving towards digitalisation for a digital economy. Review of applied management and social sciences 4 (4), 823-836, 2021*

A shift on paradigm and work culture seems to be a common early challenge in the digital transformation process. It is important to invest into awareness rising and educational activities, both internally within the judiciary and externally towards the general public. In this regard, the strong commitment of judicial leadership determines the success of the entire process. Judicial leadership should understand the importance of carrying out the transformation process thoroughly and at all levels and sectors of the judiciary, including judicial, technical, bureaucratic, administrative, supervisory and capacity building areas.

AI Technology transforms the system

AI acts as a crucial catalyst for digital transformation by enabling businesses to analyze vast amounts of data, automate repetitive tasks, and personalize customer experience and innovation and efficiency of various operations, allowing companies to stay competitive in the digital age. AI algorithms can quickly process large data sets to uncover hidden pattern and generate valuable insights, informing better decision making. AI powered chat bots and virtual assistants can provide personalized customer services, Repetitive tasks like data entry, invoice processing and quality checks can be automated using AI. AI can analyze historical data to predict future trends and potential issues, allowing businesses to address challenges.¹⁰

AI can segment customer bases based on demographics and behaviours to deliver targeted marketing campaigns with greater advances. Higher education institutions need to set clear goals for how they want to use AI, whether it is for making administrative tasks more efficient. By setting measurable objectives and aligning them with the school's mission, administrators must ensure that AI initiatives are purposeful and focused. Teachers need to learn how to use AI tools effectively and understand how AI can enhance traditional teaching methods. As we are aware, AI is constantly evolving, it is essential that teachers stay updated with latest AI advancements and teaching strategies through engaging professional development programs. Primary & Higher education must have the right technology in place to support AI.

At primary level use of AI platforms that can grow and adapt changes. Regular evaluation and feedback from students and teachers are crucial for assessing the impact of AI and making necessary improvements, ensuring that AI tools enhance the educational

¹⁰ Ahn J Michael & Chen Che Ahn J Michael & Chen Che Yu. *Digital Transformation toward AI augmented public administration: The perception of Government employees and the willingness to use AI in Government*

experience for teacher & students both. AI is also set to revolutionize administrative tasks in education.¹¹

Disadvantages of Digital transformation

- 1) ***Complexity and fragmentation:*** Digital transformation lead to increased complexity and fragmentation for instances, business, health & education sector adopt variety of new technologies which can lead to a more complex overall system. Many companies use AI and automated data management to consolidate their technology stack and build a cohesive data architecture.
- 2) ***Lack of Standardization:*** Digital transformation is still a new concept there are no industry wide standards for how it should be implemented. Lack of standardization can make it difficult for business to compare different solutions and ultimately choose the best approach for their needs. Digital transformation is not a one size fits all concepts, so business can approach it at different scales and paces depending on their size, level of digital maturity, specific business needs, and unique value drivers more.
Moreover, business can contribute to the development of standards as it relates to key technologies within AI, IoT, big data & more.
- 3) ***High Costs:*** Many business owners believe that a major disadvantage of digital transformation is that it can be costly to implement. For Instance, your businesses will need to invest in new technologies hardware & Software and guide employees on how to use these new tools. Digital transformation often requires businesses to reevaluate their existing processes and procedures, there can be significant costs associated with assessing and making changes. For example, companies that take an incremental approach are able to invest conservatively in technology and make progress while seeing a return on investment from early stage innovations.
- 4) ***Risk of Failure:*** Digital transformation represents a significant change for businesses; there is always the risk that it will fail. Businesses implement new technologies or change their processes there is always the potential for things to go wrong, and if a digital transformation initiative does not go as planned, it can lead to significant financial losses for business. If planning a large transformation of several business components, and using new technology and processes in core

¹¹ Holmstrom, Jonny. (2022). *From AI to digital transformation : The AI readiness framework. Business 65(3), 329 – 329, 2022*

business functions all at once, the risk of failure will be much higher compared to a small incremental change.¹²

5) *Disruption of employees*: Digital transformation can also cause disruptions for employees, as they may need to learn new ways of working. Additionally, the implementation of new technologies can lead to job losses, as some positions may become redundant.¹³ This disruption can cause stress and anxiety for employees, which can impact their productivity and morale.

To reduce the burden on employees, companies should be transparent about their transformation goals and the steps that need to be taken along the way. Managers should always keep employees informed and get buy in from senior staff members.

6) *Loss of customer trust*: Another potential downfall of digital transformation is loss of customer trust that can occur which businesses make changes to their system or processes. If customers are not comfortable with the changes that have been made, they may take their business elsewhere. This loss of trust can be difficult to recover from and can damage a business's reputation.

7) *Data Security Concerns*: Another disadvantage of digital transformation is the increased risks of data breaches & cyber attacks. As business increasingly store data electronically, they became more vulnerable to attacks from hackers who could gain access to the information. Additionally, as more data is shared between employees and systems, the potential for human error increases, this could lead to data being leaked accidentally.¹⁴

8) *Increase the customer engagement*: The most crucial area where businesses need to improve is the way they interact with their customers. Client increasingly imposing demand service support. Helping customers to understand a company's offering, simplifying the process of billing, providing better digital tools and insights

¹² Nanda K & Nurkolish majid. (2021). *Challenges of Digital Transformation on Good Governance Challenges*. Universitas Pembangunan Nasional, Indonesia.

¹³ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0040162524005201>

¹⁴ Zysman J, Feldman Stuart, Murray Jonathan, Nielsen Christian Niels & Kushida E Kenji. (2011). *the new challenge to economic governance: The digital transformation of Services*

to make better choices, allowing customers to better interaction with customer service.

- 9) *Ensuring regulatory compliance*: By digitizing information, improving document traceability simplifying facility management. Digital documents can be easily tracked and accessed by document controllers and operators. A fast and accurate response to regulatory inquiries when needed, a reduction in future fines and a reduction on existing fines if information management improvement are made. Increasing operations intelligence¹⁵, ability to predict asset performance, identify changing conditions, and evaluate investment options is a powerful advantage for business. Digital asset management enables the use of real time monitoring and data analytics, increasing operations intelligence and allowing operators to handle challenges more effectively.
- 10) *Boost employee productivity*: Digital technology can help companies to provide the correct and necessary information to employees, making effective, enhanced planning and scheduling and optimized logistics information.
- 11) *Using the advantage of the cloud*: Cloud technologies have proven their advantages for the management of company data and to stimulate collaboration between various business teams that are working on efficiency of business.¹⁶
- 12) *Market demand and changing consumer behaviors*: Changing consumer behaviours such as widespread adoption of mobile devices and social media, consumer now engage with brands across multiple channels. To fulfill the expectations, business must invest in omnichannel strategies that integrate physical and digital touch points, enabling customers to transition between them smoothly.

¹⁵ Chantillon, Maxim (2021). *A governance framework facilitating a digital transformation of the public administration*

¹⁶ Shuda, Vashima. (2017). *Leading digital transformation with e – governance competency framework. Processing of the special collection on eGovernment innovations in India, 11-17-2017*

- 13) *Competitive pressures and the need for innovation*: Digital transformation enables organizations to streamline operations, reduce costs and enhance efficiency allowing them to compete more effectively and deliver better customer value.¹⁷

Conclusion

Digital transformation consider as revolutionize tool which impact major trajectory within the system. AI system is new evolutionary digitalize tool that make everyday life easy, Research & Development became easier with the help of AI tools with the help of digital tools making system more citizen centric. Digital platforms make easier to access the services which was difficult to receive due to less accessibility. Digitalisation impact different sectors these technologies making system more transparent, accountable and responsible; as challenges excessive dependability and reliability hamper the human capacity and manpower, few government initiatives helpful to improve the digital strength & increased transparency such as MyGov, Digital India, CoWIN, DigiLocker, Cloud computing adoption and digital skill gap. AI algorithms can quickly process large sets to uncover hidden pattern & generate valuable insights. AI considers a major paradigm shift in the work culture. Digitalisation becomes prominent in the sectors like health, education and judiciary.

In healthcare sector, telemedicine, electronic health records are useful to analytically design the management system of health. Use AI in health works as bon for new treatment techniques, using data to identify student progress and identify areas of improvement and inform instructional decisions leading to more targeted teaching strategies. Utilizing online platform for real time collaboration between teacher and learner. Digital tools are capable to improve justice sector efficiently making justice system more transparent and accessible. Justice sector accelerated as government's embraced updated platform for online filling, digital processes and virtual courts. AI tools act as a crucial catalyst for digital transformation by enabling businesses tech equipped. AI can analyze historical data to predict future trends and potential issues, allowing businesses to address big changes. At the same digitalisation has its own shortcomings such as complexity and fragmentation, lack standalization, high costs, risk of failure, Disruption of employees, data security concerns, loss of customer trust, increase customer engagement, Ensuring regulatory compliance, System require balance of digitalisation as digital world can be dangerous if not use caution and Consciously.

¹⁷ Fernandes, Aninha Fara, Chaltikyan Georgi, Adib Keyrellous, Peters Helen Caton & Ortiz Novillo David.(2024). *International Journal of Medical Informatics* 189, 105510, 2024

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